

THE PROCESS OF IMPLEMENTING STUDENT-CENTERED LEARNING IN UNIVERSITIES OF KAZAKHSTAN**G.Z. Adilgazinov***Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Deputy Director of the National Institution "Independent Kazakhstan Accreditation Center"***E.K. Syzdykov***Director of the Department of Methodology, Monitoring and Quality Assurance of the National Institution "Independent Kazakhstan Accreditation Center"***T.T. Aimukhambetov***PhD of religion studies, chief expert of the Independent Kazakhstan Accreditation Center***ПРОЦЕСС ВНЕДРЕНИЯ СТУДЕНЧЕОЦЕНТРИРОВАННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ВУЗАХ КАЗАХСТАНА****Г.З. Адильгазинов***Доктор педагогических наук, профессор, заместитель директора НУ «Независимый Казахстанский аккредитационный центр»***Е.К. Сыздыков***Директор Департамента методологии, мониторинга и обеспечения качества НУ «Независимый Казахстанский аккредитационный центр»***Т.Т. Аймухамбетов***Доктор религиоведения, главный эксперт НУ «Независимый Казахстанский аккредитационный центр»***Abstract**

In the context of the modernization of higher education in Kazakhstan, the introduction of student-centered learning (SCL), which focuses on the active participation of students in the educational process, is of particular importance. The purpose of this article is to analyze the theoretical foundations and practical mechanisms for implementing SCL in domestic universities. The key principles of this approach are discussed: individualization of educational trajectories, development of critical thinking, development of skills for independent search and analysis of information, and strengthening the role of feedback between students and teachers.

Particular attention is paid to the institutional conditions necessary for the successful implementation of SCL: updating curricula, using interactive teaching methods, digitalization of the educational environment, and advanced training for faculty. The article emphasizes that the transition to a student-centered model requires a change in pedagogical culture, where the teacher acts not only as a source of knowledge but also as a facilitator, mentor, and partner in learning. Based on an analysis of the practices of Kazakhstani universities, we identified both positive results from implementing student-centered learning (increased student motivation, improved learning, and the development of soft skills) and existing challenges, including limited resources, insufficient faculty preparedness, and the need for systemic support at the educational policy level.

Thus, the implementation of student-centered learning is considered a strategic vector for the development of higher education in Kazakhstan, ensuring its competitiveness and compliance with international standards.

Аннотация

В условиях модернизации высшего образования Казахстана особое значение приобретает внедрение студентоцентрированного обучения (СЦО), ориентированного на активное участие обучающихся в образовательном процессе. Цель статьи заключается в анализе теоретических основ и практических механизмов реализации СЦО в отечественных вузах. Рассматриваются ключевые принципы данного подхода: индивидуализация образовательных траекторий, развитие критического мышления, формирование навыков самостоятельного поиска и анализа информации, а также усиление роли обратной связи между студентом и преподавателем.

Особое внимание уделяется институциональным условиям, необходимым для успешного внедрения СЦО: обновлению учебных планов, применению интерактивных методов преподавания, цифровизации образовательной среды и повышению квалификации профессорско-преподавательского состава. В статье подчеркивается, что переход к студентоцентрированной модели требует изменения педагогической культуры, где преподаватель выступает не только источником знаний, но и фасилитатором, наставником и партнёром в обучении.

На основе анализа практики казахстанских вузов выявлены как положительные результаты внедрения СЦО (рост мотивации студентов, повышение качества усвоения материала, развитие soft skills), так и существующие трудности — ограниченные ресурсы, недостаточная готовность преподавателей и необходимость системной поддержки на уровне образовательной политики.

Таким образом, реализация студентоцентрированного обучения рассматривается как стратегический вектор развития высшего образования Казахстана, обеспечивающий его конкурентоспособность и соответствие международным стандартам.

Keywords: student-centered learning, higher education in Kazakhstan, educational trajectory, interactive teaching methods, digitalization of education, pedagogical culture, student motivation, quality of education.

Ключевые слова: студентоцентрированное обучение, высшее образование Казахстана, образовательная траектория, интерактивные методы преподавания, цифровизация образования, педагогическая культура, мотивация студентов, качество обучения.

Higher education is undergoing significant changes in the modern world, and one of the key trends is the transition from the traditional teacher-centered model to student-centered learning (SCL). This approach places the student, their individual needs, interests, and developmental trajectory at the center of the educational process. SCL aims to develop students' critical thinking skills, independence, creativity, and the ability to engage in lifelong learning. In the context of global competition and national development strategies, the implementation of SCL is becoming a priority for Kazakhstan's universities, as it directly impacts the quality of specialist training and their competitiveness in the labor market.

The purpose of this article is to evaluate the implementation of student-centered learning in Kazakhstan's universities based on empirical data obtained during accreditation procedures. The primary empirical base is the reports of external expert groups of the Independent Kazakhstan Accreditation Center on 14 domestic higher education institutions, completed as part of specialized and institutional accreditation in 2024.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were defined:

1. To identify the overall picture and typical problems that universities face when implementing SCL.
2. To analyze specific examples of successful implementation and systemic shortcomings at the level of individual universities.
3. To summarize the data obtained and formulate conclusions, as well as to propose practical recommendations for educational organizations and the authorized body in the field of higher education.

The object of the study is the process of ensuring the quality of higher education through the use of accreditation procedures, and the subject is the process and results of the implementation of student-centered learning in accredited educational organizations.

The research methodology is based on a qualitative approach, including thematic analysis and data synthesis from reports, as well as comparison of identified practices to identify common trends and unique characteristics.

The structure of the paper includes an introduction, two main sections (a description of the key ideas of student-centered learning and a detailed analysis of universities), and a conclusion containing key findings and recommendations. This approach will allow for a comprehensive examination of the current state of student-centered learning in Kazakhstan and identify paths for its further improvement.

Student-centered learning has its roots in the early 20th century, when it was proposed by F.H. Hayward in 1905.[1] It was further developed in the works of John Dewey (1956). In the 1980s, Carl Rogers transformed SCL into an educational theory based on the principles of humanistic psychology, which proposes

learner-centered (person-centered) learning, opposed to the traditional, authoritarian system. Rogers believed that every person has an innate desire for growth and self-actualization , and education should be a facilitating environment where students actively participate in the learning process, make independent decisions and develop their inner potential.[2] SCL is also associated with the works of Jean Piaget (developmental learning) [3] and Malcolm Knowles (self-directed learning) [4].

In Soviet pedagogy and psychology, student-centered learning is closely linked to the student-centered approach, the ideas of collaborative pedagogy (Amonashvili Sh.A., Ilyin E.N., Shatalov V.F., and others), developmental learning (Vygotsky's zone of proximal development), Davydov V.V., Zankov L.V., and Elkonin D.B. They are all united by key ideas, including the active participation of the student in his or her learning and development, freedom of choice, creative activity, and collaborative work with the teacher, the development of critical and theoretical thinking, and an individual approach to each student.

The handbook " **Student-Centred Learning. A Guide for Students, Staff and Higher Education Institutions. European Students' Union. Brussels, October 2010**" provides the following definition: "Student-centred learning represents both a way of thinking and a culture within a particular higher education institution and an approach to teaching that is broadly linked to a learning theory based on constructivism. It is characterized by innovative teaching methods that aim to promote learning based on collaboration between teachers and students, promoting an active role for students in controlling their own learning process, thus contributing to the development of personal skills such as problem solving, critical and reflective thinking." [5;5]

In our thematic analysis, we will use this definition as the basis for analyzing and summarizing the activities of accredited educational programs. An analysis of the extensive scientific literature on student-centered learning allowed us to identify the following components of student-centered learning:

1. Equal student participation in governance:

Student representatives should be involved in all decisions concerning their social and academic activities, including serving on appeals committees, internal audit working groups, and curriculum development boards. In the IKCA's specialized accreditation standards, this component is assessed through an analysis of the criteria of Standard 1—Policy for Quality Assurance of the Educational Program; Standard 3—Student-Centered Learning, Teaching, and Assessment; Standard 7—Information Management and Public Dissemination; and Standard 8—Regular Monitoring, Periodic Evaluation of Educational Programs, and Periodic Accreditation.

2. **Flexible curricula and individual learning paths** are one of the key components of student-centred learning, which we have included in the criteria of Standard 2 – Development and approval of educational programmes, Standard 3 – Student-centred learning, teaching and assessment, Standard 6 – Resources and student support, and Standard 8 – Regular monitoring, periodic evaluation of educational programmes, periodic accreditation.

3. **Expected learning outcomes (ELs)** are a set of competencies that express what students will know, understand, and be able to do upon completion of the learning process. These competencies include both professional and core competencies. The analysis and evaluation of criteria for almost all IKCA Accreditation Standards focuses on this component of the SCL. The most prominent criteria are those of Standard 2—Development and Approval of Educational Programs; Standard 3—Student-Centered Learning, Teaching, and Assessment; and Standard 4—Student Admission, Academic Performance, Recognition, and Qualifications.

4. **Assessment and feedback** at the end of learning activities should be two-way. Through transparent feedback, students assess whether expected learning outcomes have been achieved and actively participate in defining and revising them for subsequent groups of students in the same course. Teachers, in turn, assess whether students have achieved the minimum requirements, as well as any additional learning outcomes, which will then be included in the Diploma Supplement. This component of the SCL, closely related to the previous one, is assessed more closely when analyzing the criteria of Standard 3 – Student-Centred Learning, Teaching, and Assessment, and Standard 4 – Student Admission, Progress, Recognition, and Qualifications.

5. **Student awareness of student-centered learning.** All students, regardless of their major or year of study, should be aware of student-centered learning. They should understand the concept, its principles, and its components. The analysis and assessment of this component is primarily based on the criteria of Standard 1 – Quality Assurance Policy for the Educational Program, Standard 3 – Student-Centered Learning, Teaching, and Assessment, and Standard 4 – Student Admissions, Academic Performance, Recognition, and Qualifications.

6. **Professional development of teachers.** Professional development programs for teachers should be aimed at ensuring that they are able to apply a variety of innovative teaching methods, tailored to the learning styles and needs of different student groups, and that they possess competencies in inclusive education. The criteria of Standard 5 – Faculty – focus heavily on the analysis and evaluation of this important component of the SCL.

7. **The use of information and communication technologies for the development of the SCLS and the technological automation of the educational process.** To analyze and evaluate this crucial component of the SCLS, the IKCA primarily uses the criteria of Standard 6 – Resources and Student Support, and

Standard 7 – Information Management and Public Information.

8. **Student Participation in Quality Assurance.** Active student participation should be a mandatory principle of quality assurance in educational institutions. Students should be recognized as competent and equal partners and serve as active members of decision-making bodies for internal and external quality assurance. The IKCA uses the criteria of Standard 1 – Policy for Quality Assurance of the Educational Program, Standard 2 – Development and Approval of Educational Programs, Standard 3 – Student-Centered Learning, Teaching, and Assessment, and Standard 8 – Regular Monitoring, Periodic Evaluation of Educational Programs, and Periodic Accreditation to analyze and evaluate quality assurance for the implementation of this component of student-centered learning.

9. **Internal assessment of the quality of assessment methods.** As part of the internal assessment of program quality, the university must pay special attention to the quality of assessment methods. This should emphasize the student's learning outcomes compared to the expected learning outcomes formulated during the curriculum development process. To analyze and assess this aspect, the IKCA uses the criteria of Standard 1 - Educational Program Quality Assurance Policy, Standard 3 - Student-Centered Learning, Teaching, and Assessment, and Standard 4 - Student Admissions, Academic Performance, Recognition, and Qualifications.

10. **Social Dimension.** The social dimension should become an integral part of the educational process and concern not only access to higher education but also successful progression through all levels, encompassing all periods of the student life cycle at each level. One of the most important elements in this regard is the adaptation of teaching methods to different student groups. It is essential to consider the individual characteristics and learning styles of different student groups, particularly students from disadvantaged backgrounds, students with special educational needs, including those with disabilities, or young parents. To analyze and evaluate quality assurance in this aspect, the IKCA uses the criteria of Standard 3 – Student-Centered Learning, Teaching, and Assessment; Standard 4 – Student Admission, Academic Performance, Recognition, and Qualifications; Standard 5 – Teaching Staff; and Standard 6 – Resources and Student Support.

11. **Student support services.** Working students or those with children should be provided with opportunities for creating a more flexible learning path and possibly allowing you to extend your studies in order to effectively combine studies, work and/or family. Students should have free access to appropriate research and teaching equipment during their studies, receive timely information about changes in the educational process, and receive academic support in the event of problems meeting academic requirements. The IKCA uses criteria from a number of standards to analyze and evaluate quality assurance for this component of the SCL: Standard 3 – Student-Centered Learning, Teaching, and Assessment; Standard 4 – Student Admissions,

Academic Performance, Recognition, and Qualifications; Standard 6 – Student Resources and Support; and Standard 7 – Information Management and Public Outreach.

12. Student mobility. This crucial component of the SCL, aligned with one of the key requirements of the Bologna Process for the internationalization of education, is typically included in the Development Strategies of Higher Education Institutions. Therefore, to analyze and assess the quality of this component of the SCL, the IKCA uses the criteria of Standard 1 – Policy for Quality Assurance of the Educational Program; Standard 3 – Student-Centered Learning, Teaching, and Assessment; Standard 4 – Student Admission, Academic Performance, Recognition, and Qualifications; and Standard 5 – Faculty.

13. Recognition. Credits earned through academic mobility and informal learning should be recognized without bureaucratic delays. A Diploma Supplement (DS), certifying the student's qualifications, including the learning outcomes and context, should be issued automatically and free of charge upon completion or upon request before completion at each higher education institution. The document should follow a standard model, clearly stating the learning outcomes achieved, including any additional credits and/or unforeseen learning outcomes. To analyze and evaluate this aspect of the SCL, the IKCA uses the criteria of Standard 3—Student-Centered Learning, Teaching, and Assessment, and Standard 4—Student Admission, Progress, Recognition, and Qualifications.

Analysis of EEG reports within the framework of the SCL

Since our goal is to identify the overall picture and typical problems that universities face when implementing student-centered learning, in order to comply with the requirements for confidentiality of information obtained during the accreditation process by the Independent Kazakhstan Center of Accreditation (IKCA) of educational organizations and educational programs in this thematic analysis, we will encode the names of specific universities using letter designations.

University A claims to attract specialists in the 6B06138 "Information Systems" program, but in reality, faculty lack opportunities for international academic mobility. The lack of an internship program for faculty and the fragmented nature of research topics and publications indicate an unsystematic approach to staff development, which undermines the ability to implement such a crucial requirement for student-centered learning as professional development for faculty, which directly impacts the quality of student learning.

University B faces challenges in implementing specialized learning environments in programs including **6B03201** "Journalism," **6B04104** "Finance," **6B04103** "Economics," and **6B04101** "Management." Students in these programs do not participate in academic mobility, and research is weak, with specialized classrooms underequipped. However, a multimedia journalism studio and an educational television studio are effectively utilized.

As in other accredited universities, the social dimension is effectively implemented in terms of inclusive education and access to education for individuals with disabilities. The university's Legal Consultation Clinic has provided positive experiences in providing free psychological support and legal consultations to students. Unfortunately, the lack of student involvement in the development of educational programs violates one of the most important requirements of the SCL—"equal student participation in governance." Specifically, student representatives should actively participate in appeals committees, internal audit working groups, and boards responsible for curriculum development.

The private institution "University C" is demonstrating positive trends. A robust system of specialized classrooms and the active involvement of corporate partners in practical training demonstrate a high-quality, practice-oriented approach. Social support for students, particularly those with disabilities, and a wide range of grants and benefits in accordance with the Regulation on Social Support for Students make education more accessible, an important element of the SCL.

Effective work is underway to achieve expected learning outcomes through external program reviews by employers, evaluation, and feedback through regular student surveys and questionnaires to revise program content with the participation of students, graduates, and employers. Serious attention is paid to the professional development of faculty through internships, internal professional development through weekly educational and methodological seminars, and a mentoring system.

The University of D provides ample opportunities for external and internal academic mobility of students with well-established procedures for credit transfer and recognition of earned credits.

To implement the requirement of a "social dimension," to improve social protection and the standard of living of students, the university has a Social Package, which provides benefits for tuition fees, financial assistance in various family and health circumstances, and incentives for high performance in academic, athletic, research, and social activities.

The university places particular emphasis on supporting socially vulnerable students, providing them with targeted social support and socio-psychological assistance:

- more than 25 students were awarded an internal rector's grant;
- 31 students (orphans) received monthly assistance in the form of financial assistance for food and clothing (up to 100 thousand).
- orphans and disabled students live in student houses free of charge.

The university places great emphasis on incentivizing faculty and staff for their professionalism and dedication. A system of financial incentives for faculty based on rankings and KPIs has been developed and implemented.

Feedback has been established between students and the university administration through the functioning of blogs (rector, deans, admissions committee).

The system for assessing relationships with students and employers and analyzing their needs is designed in such a way that learning outcomes are updated or changed in accordance with the results of a survey of employer satisfaction with the level of training of graduates.

The main drawback of this university is the lack of practical training in classes, for example, in the 7M05101 "Biology with Fundamentals of Microbiology" program. This deprives students of applied knowledge and discrepancies between student learning outcomes and the demands of the modern labor market. The university's educational programs have only just begun to implement micro-qualifications, which reduces the potential for flexible programs and individualized educational trajectories.

University E ensures the successful implementation of the SCL. Assessment and feedback during systematic quality monitoring through surveys on satisfaction with learning outcomes enables, with the participation of students and employers, changes to educational programs regarding planned learning outcomes and assessment methods. The successful implementation of the external and internal academic mobility program demonstrates an effective approach to meeting student needs. Student support services, like those at other accredited universities, operate effectively, ensuring inclusive education for individuals with disabilities: like all 13 other universities, tactile pathways, ramps, lifts, and designated parking spaces are available. Social support is provided to students from vulnerable groups (orphans, those from large low-income families, and individuals with disabilities). As in other universities accredited by the IKCA, this university implements a high level of use of information and communication technologies, licensed educational programs such as AutoCAD, MidasCivil, and others. Technological automation of the educational process is carried out using the automated information system "Platonus".

However, as in other universities, insufficient attention is paid to timely work to inform students about the features of student-centered learning in accredited educational programs. Therefore, students are formally involved in the work of the Academic Council and academic committees for the development of educational programs.

Institution "University F"

To ensure equal participation in governance, the university has developed a system for assessing the effectiveness of its mission, goals, and objectives. This system is implemented across all departments and involves all employees, external stakeholders, and students. The university has a well-developed internal quality assurance system, a culture of academic integrity, and a functioning quality management system.

Regarding expected learning outcomes, for example, the 6B05202 Ecology (Bachelor's) program is developed within the context of a competency-based model of specialist training and is focused on learning outcomes expressed as competencies. The program is designed using a modular principle. Each module is focused on achieving a specific learning outcome, that is,

a competency. Learning outcomes are formulated for the program as a whole, for each module, and for each individual course.

In the 2022-2023 academic year, the final assessment format was revised: a thesis project was introduced, resulting in the student's work representing an independent solution to applied problems relevant to the educational program profile, completed using project-based approaches such as business projects, models, creative projects, and other projects. A QR code encryption system was introduced, using combined forms of the comprehensive exam.

To carry out assessment, feedback, and identify stakeholder needs, the university receives from employers, for example, letters of gratitude for the training of students in the "Standardization, Certification, and Metrology (by Industry)" program, expert opinions on the educational program 6B07502 "Standardization, Certification, and Metrology (by Industry)", etc.

Academic mobility among students is poorly developed (external mobility is completely absent). Student engagement in research is low. The university's website lacks information about students' research activities, certificates, or diplomas—that is, supporting documents confirming students' involvement in research.

To support the professional development of young teachers, the university has established and operates a "Young Teacher School," which oversees the work of newly arrived teachers and provides them with methodological support.

Information support for students and teachers is provided on the basis of the Information and Analytical Complex for Managing the Educational Process "Electronic Rector's Office" and the official website <http://nku.edu.kz>, which are integrated with each other.

The University faces problems with academic mobility and research work in the programs 6B05202 "Ecology", 6B07502 "Standardization, Certification and Metrology (by industry)", 6B07302 "Design and Information Modeling of Construction Projects".

At the Institution "University G", in the direction of the SCL "Equal Participation of Students in Management", master's students of the EP "7M04112 - State and Local Government" take part in the management of the university, are part of collegial bodies, make proposals for making management decisions, improving the educational and methodological, scientific and educational process.

Students as part of its "Assessment and Feedback" system. This method is characterized by capturing and assessing expectations and interests related to the university's educational program. Surveys, questionnaires, and other methods are traditionally used to collect relevant information. Based on student data—identifying their interests, identifying their strengths and weaknesses, and interacting with the educational program—the prospects for a long-term development program for the educational program are determined, ensuring increased competitiveness in the educational market.

In the area of the SCL "Expected Learning Outcomes," the procedure for developing the EP "7M04112-State and Local Government" and planning

learning outcomes is carried out collegially and transparently, taking into account the scientific interests of the teaching staff, proposals from stakeholders, primarily students included in the working group of the Academic Committee, as well as existing expert opinions on the educational program.

The implementation plan for the integrated Social Dimension SCL, designed to ensure equal opportunities and accommodate individual needs in achieving learning outcomes, study additional subjects, and repay academic debt, includes a summer semester, and allows for enrollment in additional courses. The university promotes inclusive education and offers substantial support to students with disabilities and from low-income families through discounts and rector's grants. The university has created all the necessary learning conditions for individuals with special needs: library space, ramps, elevators, and designated parking spaces.

In terms of implementing the professional development of teachers, the management of EP 7M04112 "State and Local Government" pays attention to improving the qualifications and training of teaching staff in innovative educational technologies and methods that promote professional development and allow them to be constantly informed about the latest changes in their field of activity.

The university provides compensation for expenses for publication in foreign scientific journals and provides for publication in the international databases Scopus and/or Web of Science.

At the same time, this university has the same fundamental problems identified in a number of other universities - a low level of academic mobility of master's students in programs 7M04112 "Public and Local Administration" and 7M04122 "Economics ," as well as ineffective career guidance. This leads to low enrollment of master's students, indicating the programs' lack of appeal and the ineffective implementation of the vocational school system.

At the Institution "University H"

In the direction of "Expected learning outcomes", when developing the educational program 7M01703- Foreign language: two foreign languages, the principles of continuity, succession and consistent increase in requirements for learning outcomes based on competencies with the active participation of master's students in this program were used.

The system for assessing relationships with employers and analyzing their needs is designed in such a way that learning outcomes are updated or changed in accordance with the results of a survey of employer satisfaction with the level of training of graduates, in accordance with employers' proposals, using the results of a survey primarily of consumers of educational services - students.

This university is actively developing social support for students, including those with disabilities. To this end, faculty members have completed courses on inclusive education.

As in many other accredited universities, resource provision allows for the effective use of information and communication technologies for the development

of the SCL, and all the capabilities of the automated information system "Platonus" are used for the technological automation of the educational process.

However, this university lacks a systematic approach to the scientific work of teachers, which negatively affects the quality of education in the field 7M04103 "Accounting and Audit" means that an important area of the SCL—"Professional Development of Teachers"—is not being effectively implemented. The insufficient provision of educational and methodological resources for the programs is also a serious obstacle to an effective SCL.

Institution "University I"

In the area of "Expected Learning Outcomes," Academic Committees, which include students from this university, engage employer representatives when developing programs to determine learning outcomes that align with the competencies required by the modern labor market, particularly for EP 6B06202—Radio Engineering, Electronics, and Telecommunications , 6B04205—Customs, and others. Roundtables are held annually with the participation of those interested in the development and updating of the EP: student representatives, university administration, department heads, faculty, and employers. Their suggestions are necessarily taken into account when developing and updating the EP.

The university actively provides social support to students, including those with disabilities. For these students, the university has an inclusive education office equipped with the necessary teaching equipment and developed rules for ensuring inclusive education. A full-time specialist has been assigned to staff the office.

In the area of the SCL "Flexible Curricula and Individual Learning Paths," the experience of implementing the additional Minor program "Professionally Oriented English" in one of the programs has been effective.

In the "Use of Information and Communication Technologies for the Development of Information and Communication Technologies and Technological Automation of the Educational Process" program, this university has demonstrated effective experience in implementing innovative educational technologies and methods, for example, in the field of construction, which provide students with the opportunity for more effective learning and development.

1. Use of virtual and augmented reality (VR and AR):

- VR and AR allow construction trainees to immerse themselves in virtual models and simulations of construction projects. This allows them to understand construction processes and make decisions in real time.

2. BIM (Building Information Modeling):

- BIM is a modeling method that enables the creation of three-dimensional models of building projects with detail at every stage of design and construction. This improves collaboration between various project participants and contributes to process optimization.

3. Project-based learning:

- Curricula that include real-world construction projects allow students to apply their knowledge in

practice and acquire skills that will be useful in the job market. This method is used in the 3D modeling and AutoCAD disciplines.

At the same time, this university has serious problems with the implementation of the SCL: as well as in A number of other accredited universities have problems with the implementation of academic mobility of students in certain programs, formal participation of students in the internal quality assurance system, and a lack of equipped specialized classrooms for certain programs.

At University J, we were able to highlight only a few aspects of the 13 aspects of student-centered learning we identified in the reports of external expert groups. Specifically, in the "Expected Learning Outcomes" section, all five accredited programs noted the university's effective collaboration with employers in implementing practice-oriented learning, incorporating learning outcomes in demand in the modern labor market in the southern region of the country, and introducing elements of dual education in certain programs.

In the area of "Professional Development of Teachers," IKCA experts noted that the university has developed an effective system of rewarding teachers and staff for high pedagogical excellence, scientific achievements, and dedication (for example, financial incentives for the scientific work of faculty members for publishing articles in highly ranked journals). Senior faculty members are actively working on the topic of "Monitoring as a Method of Research and Forecasting the Dynamics of Ethnosocial Processes in the Republic of Kazakhstan," and research projects are consolidated at JSC NGNTsT.

However, the academic mobility plan for the "Student Mobility" program in program 6B04202 – Law Enforcement Activity has only just been developed, and no work on external or internal student mobility has been identified for program 6B01506 – Physics and Computer Science. Overall, the implementation of the SCL at this university is very low.

IN University K: In order to implement the requirements of the SCL in terms of flexible curricula, this university offers additional courses in the form of a Minor (Minor) – a set of interrelated subjects of the same profile, different from the main area of training of a teacher – for the educational program “6B01704 – Training of Teachers of Uzbek Language and Literature”.

In planning and implementing expected learning outcomes at this university, experts noted that educational programs are focused on learning outcomes. All stakeholders, including employers and students, are involved in the development of educational programs and the monitoring of educational activities within them, and they actively participate in the Academic Program Development Committees.

The "Assessment and Feedback" program at the SCL annually collects feedback from educational service consumers (employers, university graduates, students, and their parents) to determine their satisfaction with the quality of educational services and the trans-

parency of the university's operations. The feedback results are analyzed and discussed at department meetings.

In order to ensure objectivity and openness in internal and external communications, as well as in interactions with applicants, the following feedback channels are in operation: the rector's blog; call center; help-line; help boxes; and career guidance department.

To implement the "social dimension," the university has created facilities for students with disabilities (access ramps, information and navigation aids, and doors and staircases painted in contrasting colors). Conditions have been created to ensure constant access for students with disabilities and other social groups. The Empathy Center for Psychological Support in the Gagarin Academic Building provides social assistance and psychological and pedagogical support.

The assessment of the conformity of the content and learning outcomes for the recognition of a non-formal education program with the content and learning outcomes of an academic discipline or module is carried out by comparing the formulated learning outcomes and competencies of the compared programs, their volume (in academic hours and academic credits), learning objectives, and assessment of academic achievements.

The main goal of working with faculty and staff at the University is to create conditions for their professional and personal growth. This is facilitated by the development of a system of measures aimed at establishing a comprehensive professional development system for all faculty, ensuring social security for employees, and fostering a positive social environment at the university. The university uses a KPI system—a set of interrelated individual numeric indicators used to evaluate the effectiveness of the faculty.

Internal assessment of the quality of assessment methods is achieved through assessors' knowledge of student knowledge assessment methods and ongoing professional development in this area. In particular, department faculty members completed international online courses for faculty members on teaching and assessing students' knowledge of the Uzbek language and literature. Assessment methods for students' knowledge, skills, and abilities contribute to the achievement of learning outcomes. Methodological recommendations for assessing assignments in the disciplines of the "Training of Teachers of the Uzbek Language and Literature" program have been developed.

To help students understand the specifics of the SCL, the university's website features a "Guide for First-Year Students," which contains information on the basic principles of credit-based learning, the organization and design of the educational process, students' rights and responsibilities, and the activities of advisors.

As the analysis shows, in this university a significantly larger number of SCL elements have been implemented in its activities.

At the University In the direction of the SCL "Equal Participation of Students in Management", external audit experts noted the active participation of students, along with members of the Academic Council,

the Academic Committee, which includes students, the Education Department of the Karaganda Region, and preschool organizations in the implementation, monitoring, and revision of the internal quality assurance system of the educational program.

In the plan for implementing the SCL requirement "Expected learning outcomes", it was revealed that the accredited programs of this university were developed in the context of a competency-based model for training specialists, with competencies corresponding to the Dublin descriptors, taking into account ECTS and the EPVO qualification framework.

In accordance with the requirements for the implementation of inclusive education, the subject "Inclusive Education" has been included in all pedagogical educational programs, and teachers who have completed advanced training in inclusive education are involved in teaching it. A minor has been added to the main program. Program on the features of inclusive education.

In the implementation plan for the composite SCL "Assessment and Feedback", programs are reviewed annually based on an analysis of feedback received from students, employers, graduates and other stakeholders.

The audit revealed that students and employers have repeatedly initiated the introduction of disciplines relevant to the teaching labor market into educational programs. For example, the inclusion of the discipline "Monitoring the Individual Development of Preschool and Primary School-Age Children" demonstrates how proposals from educational stakeholders are quickly reflected in curricula.

The implementation of academic mobility for students is supported, which is regulated by the University's Academic Policy, which provides for the development of a culture of flexible educational trajectories, the development of mechanisms for mutual recognition and the transfer of courses and periods of study, qualifications and degrees in other universities.

To implement the "Recognition" requirement of the SCL, the university provides the opportunity to recognize competencies acquired through non-formal and informal learning, such as internships, professional practice, or independent learning, using competency assessment and verification mechanisms. Recognition of academic credits for mobility purposes is based on the following documents: contract, training agreement; transcript of grades; and internship completion certificate.

As part of the implementation of the "Professional Development of Teachers" component of the SCL, over the past five years, departmental faculty has completed 85 professional development courses. The university provides faculty with the opportunity to participate in internships abroad to exchange experiences with international colleagues. Faculty participates in courses at the Center for Distance Education Technologies, developing the necessary skills for working with the credit-based learning system.

Moral and material incentive systems are in place for faculty. Clear career ladders and development plans have been developed for faculty, allowing them to build

long-term plans for the university. A differentiation coefficient for the incentive salary supplement per academic year has been introduced, and individuals are recognized in specific categories, such as the "Best Curator-Advisor" award for the 2020-2021 academic year.

In implementing the "Social Dimension" SCL requirement, special attention is paid to creating conditions for the education of individuals with special educational needs: an inclusive education room has been equipped with modern equipment. This room allows for classes to be conducted with the needs of students with disabilities in mind. A unique collection of materials is available for individuals with visual, hearing, and musculoskeletal impairments. This includes large-print books, electronic audio materials, as well as special workstations, specialized desks, ramps, and digital devices that facilitate access to learning.

At the Institution "University As part of the SCL's "Equal Participation of Students in Management" program, experts noted student participation in assessing the quality of teaching and educational programs through surveys and questionnaires, active student involvement in managing the educational process, and the development of proposals for its improvement. Students are members of the Academic and Methodological Council and the Academic Quality Council. According to interviews, the university regularly holds meetings between students, faculty, and the rector to discuss student issues. Students can meet with the rector at any time during the working day, regardless of the time.

In the area of the SCL "Flexible Curricula and Individual Learning Paths" at this university, for example, the accredited EP 6B01422 - "Physical Education and Sport" offers the following individual learning paths: "Theory and Methods of Teaching Physical Education and Sport", "Fundamentals of Teaching Sports Disciplines (Sports Trainer Path)"; "Fitness and Sport" (Fitness Instructor and Healthy Lifestyle Specialist Path), "Management in the Field of Physical Education and Sport".

Through the Student Mobility program, the university implements opportunities for external and internal academic mobility with established procedures for credit transfer and recognition. For example, from 2022 to 2024, a total of 251 students completed external, internal, outgoing, and incoming academic mobility across all programs at the Institute of Pedagogy, Business, and Law, including 114 in the pedagogical program.

To implement the SCL program's "Student Awareness with Student-Centered Learning" program, the university traditionally holds an orientation week for first-year and international students, where they are thoroughly introduced to the university's Academic Policy and the specifics of the student-centered approach to learning.

As part of the implementation of the "Recognition" component of the SCL, if learning outcomes are consistent with the prerequisites of the educational program, individual courses from the previous level of formal education, other types of academic work, and informal learning outcomes are transferred. For example,

students who have completed one or more courses on the Coursera platform and received certificates will have their credits subsequently counted towards their educational achievements (20 students from the accredited educational program completed the ICT course on Coursera).

In the implementation plan for the next component of the SCL—"Professional Development of Teachers"—teachers in accredited programs conduct classes using innovative technologies and methods. Two teachers completed courses on inclusion at the National Women's Pedagogical University. Systematic assessment of teacher competence and evaluation of teaching effectiveness at the university as a whole and within departments is implemented through:

- internal assessment (open classes, mutual visits, control visits);
- identifying the opinions of internal consumers (students) about the quality of educational services and the level of competence of the teaching staff;
- external assessment (employer surveys). The university has developed an interconnected system for assessing the effectiveness of teaching quality.

In the "Expected Learning Outcomes" section of the SCL, "University M" operates a system for assessing relationships with employers and analyzing their needs, so that learning outcomes are updated or changed in accordance with the results of a survey on employer satisfaction with the level of training of graduates and students of all programs. During the audit, external audit experts obtained evidence of the participation of students, faculty, and other stakeholders in the development of the educational program and ensuring its quality.

Basic, specialized, and elective disciplines of the educational program 6B04217 "Jurisprudence" are mastered in light of the latest advances in science and practice, which ensures the relevance of the taught disciplines and a clear

compliance with the objectives of the educational program.

The law programs offer practice-oriented training at the department's branches in the Akmola Regional Court and the Akmola Region Department of Justice. Experienced instructors with practical experience in the prosecutor's office, law enforcement, the judicial system, forensics, notarial work, and advocacy work to master the practical aspects of the subjects.

The program 6B02111 "Design" also implemented a practice-oriented approach to training, classes conducted by leading employees of enterprises and organizations of the region (designer of the regional branch of the "Union of Artists of the Republic of Karelia", designer of the advertising and production company "OLIVIN", designer of the advertising agency "DEI").

As part of the "Social Dimension" and "Student Support Services" programs, the university has established a unique Institute of Exempt Curators—the only one in the northern region—which serves as the primary structure monitoring student attendance and academic performance and implementing educational work. Counselors are available at night in the Student

Houses, and social support is provided to students, including those with disabilities. Furthermore, as at other accredited universities, the Student Service Center operates, providing approximately 20 types of services. Construction of the Student Palace and a sports complex, which meets international standards, has been completed. A legal clinic is actively operating, and the laboratory facilities and forensic testing ground are effectively used for joint classes between lecturers and industrial practitioners.

The "Professional Development of Teachers" program at the SCL provides an ongoing system of professional development for faculty using modern information technology approaches (courses in artificial intelligence, neural networks, online and offline teaching methods, etc.). Innovative teaching methods are used, taking into account European experience in conducting classes. Professional development courses offered through the Belgian Education Council have facilitated the application of effective teaching methods, the development of assessment criteria, the implementation of formative assessment, and the stimulation of student reflection. Mentoring is part of all programs, and professional development activities are held for young teachers.

The results of the department's current research, conducted as part of the research school "Theory and Practice of Applying National Legislation in the Context of Legal Reform in the Republic of Kazakhstan," are also being integrated into the educational process. A faculty incentive system based on monthly ratings has been developed, along with a well-established system for in-house professional development (weekly educational and methodological seminars).

The big picture and typical problems

Overall, universities are striving to implement SCLs, but they face a number of systemic challenges. The most common shortcomings include:

1. Regrettably, we note a **formal, superficial approach to the implementation of the two interrelated components of the SCL: "Equal Student Participation in Management" and "Student Participation in Quality Assurance."** The inclusion of one active student (master's or doctoral student) on the Academic Council, Academic Council, or Academic Program Development Committee does not automatically guarantee the implementation of this aspect of the SCL. Clearly, not just one student, but several of the most responsible, authoritative, critically thinking student representatives capable of expressing and defending their position should be included in such councils, committees, and working groups.

2. **Insufficient work in** accredited universities and programs to implement the minor, micro-qualifications, and nano-credits required by the State Compulsory Education Standard (SCS) would allow students to more effectively develop their educational trajectory, acquiring the professional competencies necessary for the modern labor market. These are problems with the implementation of the "Flexible Curricula and Individual Learning Paths" component of the SCS. However, many accredited programs do provide individual trajectories.

3. In the implementation of such an important component of the SCL as "Expected Learning Outcomes" IKCA experts note that program developers have mastered the art of formulating learning outcomes and correctly define methods for assessing the development of learning outcomes during midterm and final assessments. However, a **lack of practice-oriented training is noted**: universities inconsistently engage practitioners, creating a gap between theory and the actual needs of the labor market. Although many universities in the Republic of Kazakhstan are actively working to introduce elements of dual education, no such effective practice has been identified in the programs of the 16 universities accredited by the IKCA.

4. According to experts, the "Assessment and Feedback" function of the SCL is implemented at the required level thanks to, firstly, the use of automated information systems (Platonus, Univer, etc.), which enable students to achieve transparent assessment, track their academic performance, and rank; secondly, well-established monitoring of all aspects of students' educational activities, surveys of educational stakeholders regarding satisfaction with their results, and decision-making on identified issues; and thirdly, the use of information and communication technologies, university websites, and social media (WhatsApp , etc.) for prompt feedback .

5. A review and analysis of external audit reports reveals that universities are underperforming in the most important component of the Student Centered Learning (SCL) system—students' awareness of student-centered learning. Although we have noted the universities' experience in conducting an orientation week for new students, there is no information from experts indicating that they clearly and unambiguously communicate the essence and content of this learning approach to students, nor that they understand students' ability to manage their own educational trajectories. This is clearly why we have noted the long-standing problem of **low academic mobility among students and faculty**.

This is the most acute and common shortcoming. At many universities, students and faculty lack sufficient opportunities to participate in exchange programs, which limits their professional development. This is most often due to a lack of funding for mobility programs, insufficient efforts by departments to find opportunities for students to earn the necessary credits at national and international universities, and, finally, students' ignorance of opportunities to earn the credits they seek at other national universities and universities in neighboring and distant countries.

6. The next component of the SCL, "Recognition," related to mobility, is reflected in reports from external expert groups as having been implemented in terms of recognizing student credits earned through the minimal mobility process noted above. However, unfortunately, widespread experience with recognizing informal education, similar to Coursera programs , has not been found in accredited universities and programs. Although This one from important components of the SCL.

7. In the next important component of the SCL, "Professional Development of Teachers," all accredited universities and programs are implementing the necessary internal and external professional development for teachers, and it is gratifying to note that serious attention is paid to inclusive education. Rankings, material and moral incentives, and the implementation of KPI-based performance assessments are used to stimulate and motivate the professional development of faculty . However, reports from external expert groups only noted the use of innovative educational technologies by teachers, emphasizing the organization of active, independent cognitive activity in students, the development of critical thinking, and technologies that prepare them for independent, lifelong learning.

8. All accredited universities and educational programs effectively utilize information and communication technologies, and have the appropriate software and computer equipment. Technological automation of the educational process has been implemented, leveraging the capabilities of the automated information systems "Platonus," "Univer," and others, and educational portals are operational. University websites, electronic document management, email, and social media are also used to promptly inform participants in the educational process and provide feedback.

9. In terms of implementing the next important component of the Social Dimension SCL, we have already noted the universities' work on inclusive education, adapting teaching methods to different student groups. All universities are creating the best possible conditions for students with disabilities, working students, and young parents, and faculty are receiving advanced training in organizing inclusive education. All universities offer tuition benefits for orphans, students from large families, and students from low-income families, and rector's grants are awarded. Free legal and psychological counseling is also available. This work needs to be continued and expanded.

10. A careful analysis of external expert group reports and self-assessment reports allows us to note that, in our opinion, IKCA-accredited universities and programs are paying insufficient attention to such an important component of the SCL as "Internal Assessment of the Quality of Assessment Methods." Unfortunately, for many years, since 1996, many universities have been using testing, primarily computer-based, for assessment. Obviously, due to the specific nature of the academic disciplines, it is not always necessary to use it. We have not observed any in-depth analysis of the assessment methods used by accredited universities for their compliance with the assessed learning outcomes. We believe that program directors, quality assurance departments, and accreditation bodies need to work on this issue when assessing the implementation of this aspect of the SCL.

11. In the analysis and evaluation of student support services at all IKCA-accredited universities and educational programs, no particular issues were identified: material and technical equipment is available, information and library resources meet student needs, access to electronic databases is provided, free internet access is available, dormitory space is available for out-

of-town students, and extracurricular activities are organized. Each university has effective Student Service Centers, providing up to 20 different services.

However, the EEG reports point to outdated material and technical resources at some universities and in some programs, incomplete information content on websites, and a lack of specialized classrooms.

Conclusion: Thematic analysis shows that the implementation of student-centered learning principles At Kazakhstani universities, this is a process that is at various stages of development. We see that while many universities are striving for this approach, they face a number of challenges that require careful consideration.

- **Disjointedness instead of systemicity.** The implementation of SCLs often resembles a mosaic: universities add individual, but not always interconnected, elements. For example, they may actively support social policy but overlook the importance of academic mobility or student engagement in research. This creates the feeling that individual steps are being taken, but the overall, coherent picture is not yet in place.

A formal approach. Sometimes what appears to be student-centered learning on paper turns out to be a mere formality in practice. When students' participation in research projects or interactions with practitioners is irregular, this deprives them of the real opportunity to gain valuable experience.

- **Limited opportunities.** Insufficient or complete lack of funding, a lack of international connections, low levels of foreign language proficiency, and poor interaction with the labor market can create a kind of isolation. Without these, it's harder for students to acquire the relevant knowledge and skills needed to be competitive in the future.

At the same time, it is very important to note that there are also positive examples of successful work, which we noted during our analysis of the work of each of the accredited universities.

Recommendations for educational organizations:

- Integrate the SCL into the overall strategy. It's important not just to implement individual elements, but to make the SCL part of the school's mission and vision. This means that all processes—from curricula to extracurricular activities—should be aimed at supporting students.

- More actively introduce additional programs (Minor), micro-qualifications, nano-credits into the content of educational programs, help students find opportunities for informal education within the walls of the university and outside of it (Coursera, MOOC, etc.) to acquire professional competencies that are important for the modern labor market.

- It is necessary to intensify academic mobility by seeking financial resources for this, more clearly explain to students the necessity and advantages of this

component of the SCL, strengthen students' research work, improve the material and technical base, and increase information transparency.

We need to create an atmosphere where students feel not only like learners but also active participants in the process. This includes expanding opportunities for participation in research projects, real-world cases, and international programs. We should also conduct more frequent student leadership training sessions, focusing on the most active students.

- Strengthening ties with partners. It's important to establish closer and more ongoing contacts with businesses to ensure that curricula meet employer expectations and that students gain practical experience.

Proposals to the authorized body in the field of higher and postgraduate education (Ministry of Science and Higher Education)

- Consider the possibility of creating grant mechanisms or other financial support for the activities of those universities that demonstrate significant success in implementing SCL.

- Consider the possibility of creating Platforms or events where universities could share their best practices should be created. Continue the effective practice of conducting offline and online training seminars on the implementation of SCL. This would help everyone learn from the examples of leading and successful universities.

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